

Synthesis of 6- and 7-Halogeno-2-(2-Thienyl)-Chromones and Related Compounds

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Preparation of some new 6- and 7-halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)-chromones, 1 : 3-propanediones, acrylophenones and related compounds is reported.

In recent years increasing attention has been directed to the biological activity of chromones¹⁻⁴ and chalcones. Halogeno substituted chromones with heterocyclic substituents in the 2-position are reported to have broncho-dilatory⁵, coronary-spasmolytic⁶ and anti-sarcoma-180⁷ properties, while chalcones have exhibited bacteriostatic⁸, tuberculostatic⁹ and insecticidal¹⁰ activity.

4'- and 5'-Halogeno-2'-(2-thenoyloxy)-acetophenones (I b-a) were prepared by esterification of 4'- and 5'-halogeno 2'-hydroxy-acetophenones with thenoyl chloride. The resulting esters were converted into 1 : 3-propanediones (II b & a) by Baker-Venkataraman transformation^{2,3, 7, 11, 12}. The cyclodehydration of the diones in acidic medium afforded chromones (III b-a).

Base catalysed condensation of 4'- and 5'-halogeno-*o*-hydroxy-acetophenones with 2-thiophene aldehyde yielded the corresponding acrylophenones (IV b-a) which underwent oxidative ring closure to the same chromones (III b&a) obtained by cyclodehydration of 1 : 3-propanediones.

The acrylophenones on oxidation under Alger-Flynn and Oyamada reaction conditions¹⁴⁻²⁰ gave 6- and 7-halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromones (V a & b). These acrylophenones in aqueous alcoholic solution and sodium acetate²¹ cyclised to the isomeric chromanones (VI a&b).

These compounds are being tested for their physiological activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 6'- and 7'-halogeno-2-(2-thenoyloxy)-acetophenones : (I b&a) Table No. 1 : To a mixture of 4'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone (3.42 g.) and 2-thenoyl chloride (2.94 g) was added dropwise anhydrous pyridine (4 ml) with stirring. The mixture was left overnight at room temperature. It was then poured over ice and hydrochloric acid.

The separated solid was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and finally with distilled water. The dry solid was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles (I-b). Yield 80%.

TABLE 1

4'- and 5'-Halogeno-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-acetophenones (I b&a)

Compounds	M.P. °C	Colour and Crystalline shape	Molecular formula	Found		Required	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
4'-Chloro-2'-(2-thienyloxy)- acetophenone.	90	Colourless shining needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ ClS	55.39	3.219	55.60	3.207
4'-Bromo-2'-(2-thienyloxy)- acetophenone.	87	Pinkish needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ BrS	47.90	2.711	47.99	2.706
4'-Iodo-2'-(2-thienyloxy)- acetophenone.	95	Colourless needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ IS	41.34	2.418	41.94	2.419
5'-Chloro-2'-(2-thienyloxy)- acetophenone.	91	Pale yellow plates.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ ClS	55.55	3.217	55.60	3.207
5'-Bromo-2'-(2-thienyloxy)- acetophenone.	90	Pink plates	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ BrS	47.94	2.716	47.99	2.706
5'-Iodo-2'-(2-thienyloxy)- acetophenone.	98	Pink rods	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ IS	41.88	2.422	41.94	2.419

- b) R₁ = Cl, Br and I, R₂ = H, R₃ = thienyl.
and
a) R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl, Br and I, R₃ = thienyl.

Preparation of 1 : 3-propanediones (II) (Table No. 2) : To a solution of 4'-chloro-2'-(2-thienyloxy) acetophenone (2.81 g) in anhydrous pyridine (8 ml) was added potassium hydroxide (1.68 g). The mixture was stirred for half an hour. It was then poured over ice and hydrochloric acid. The separated solid was washed with distilled water. The dry solid was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (II b). Yield 86%.

Preparation of 6- and 7-halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)-chromones (III b&a) Table No. 3 : 1-(4-chloro-2-hydroxy-phenyl)-3-(2-thienyl)-1 : 3-propanedione (1 g) was refluxed with glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 ml) for 20 mins. The mixture was then poured over ice with stirring. The separated solid was washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and finally with distilled water. The dry solid was crystallised from ethanol (III b). Yield 80%.

TABLE 2

1 : 3-Propanediones (II b&a)

Compound	M.P. °C	Colour and Crystalline shape	Molecular formula	Found		Required	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
1-(4-Chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl) 3-(2-thienyl):1 : 3-propanedione.	140	Yellow needles	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ ClS	56.01	3.250	55.60	3.207
1-(4-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl) 3-(2-thienyl)-1 : 3-propanedione.	131	Bright yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ BrS	48.06	2.744	47.99	2.707
1-(4-Iodo-2-hydroxyphenyl) 3-(2-thienyl)-1 : 3-propanedione.	136	Pale yellow rods.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ IS	41.90	2.512	41.94	2.419
1-(5-Chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl)- 3-(2-thienyl)-1 : 3-propanedione. ¹¹	112	Deep yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ ClS	55.67	3.218	55.70	3.207
1-(5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl)- 3-(2-thienyl)-1 : 3-propanedione.	92	Greenish yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ BrS	47.84	2.725	47.99	2.706
1-(5-Iodo-2-hydroxyphenyl)- 3-(2-thienyl):1 : 3-propanedione.	114	Yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ IS	41.90	2.512	41.94	2.417

¹¹ *Chemical Abstracts*, 1966, **64**, 4127e.

TABLE 3

6- and 7-Halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)-chromones (III b&a)

Compound	M.P. °C	Colour and crystalline shape	Molecular formula	Found		Required	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
7-Chloro-2-(2-thienyl)-chromone	176	Pale yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₂ ClS	59.95	2.687	59.43	2.667
7-Bromo-2-(2-thienyl)-chromone	175	Pale yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₂ BrS	50.52	2.301	50.82	2.28
7-Iodo-2-(2-thienyl)-chromone	165	Pale yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₂ SI	41.74	1.53	42.85	1.93
6-Chloro-2-(2-thienyl)-chromone ¹¹	183	Pale yellow needles	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₂ ClS	58.30	2.67	59.43	2.687
6-Bromo-2-(2-thienyl)-chromone	171	Pale yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₂ BrS	50.81	2.29	50.82	2.28
6-Iodo-2-(2-thienyl)-chromone	188	Pale yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₂ IS	42.36	1.543	42.85	1.923

¹¹ *Chemical Abstracts*, 1966, **54**, 4127e.

Preparation of 4'- and 5'-halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenones (IV b&a) Table No. 4 : To a solution of 4'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-acetophenones (1.71 g) and thiophen-2-aldehyde (1.28 g) in alcohol (15 ml) was added potassium hydroxide solution (2%, 25 ml), dropwise with cooling and stirring. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 6 hrs. It was then diluted with distilled water (10 ml) and poured over ice and hydrochloric acid. The separated solid was washed with water. The dry solid was crystallised from alcohol in yellow shining needles (IV b). Yield 60%.

Preparation of 6- and 7-halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)-chromones (III b&a) Table No. 3 : To a mixture of 4'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone (1.5 g), amyl alcohol (10 ml) and selenium dioxide (1 g) was refluxed at 150° for 15 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled, and filtered to remove selenium formed during the reaction. The filtrate was washed with

TABLE 4

4'- and 5'-Halogeno-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenones (V b&a)

Compounds	M.P. °C	Colour and crystalline shape	Molecular formula	Found		Required	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
4'-Chloro-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone.	107	Yellow shining needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ ClS	59.29	3.498	58.98	3.402
4'-Bromo-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone.	104	Orange red rod	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ BrS	50.13	2.924	50.48	2.912
4'-Iodo-2'-(hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone.	109	Pinkish yellow rods.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ IS	43.70	2.534	43.82	2.524
5'-Chloro-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone ¹³	115	Yellow shining plates.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ ClS	59.29	3.431	58.98	3.420
5'-Bromo-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone.	120	Orange red needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ BrS	50.32	3.000	59.48	2.912
5'-Iodo-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone.	120	Pinkish yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ IS	43.99	2.714	43.82	2.527

¹³. *Chemical Abstracts*, 1964, 1683.

dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove the unchanged acrylophenone. It was then steam distilled to remove steam volatile amyl alcohol. The nonsteam-volatile portion was extracted with ether. The solid obtained on the evaporation of ether was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles (III b). Yield 18%.

Preparation of 6- and 7-halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromones (V b&a), Table No. 5: 4'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-(2'-thienyl)-acrylophenone (1.5 g) was dissolved in alcohol (15 ml) and 2% sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml) was added with cooling. The reaction flask was held in ice-water and hydrogen peroxide (20 vol. 20 ml) was added in portions with shaking. The flask was tightly stoppered and kept at room temperature for 6 hrs. The orange red colour of the reaction mixture changed to lemon yellow. It was then poured over ice and hydrochloric acid. The separated solid was washed with water. The dry solid was crystallised from alcohol in greenish yellow needles (V b), Table No. 5. Yield 55%.

TABLE 5

6- and 7-Halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)3-hydroxy-chromones (V b&a)

Compounds	M.P. °C	Colour and crystalline shape	Molecular formula	Found		Required	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
7-Chloro-2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromone.	200	Greenish yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₃ ClS	56.31	2.554	56.02	2.514
7-Bromo-2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromone.	200	Brownish yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₃ BrS	48.52	2.302	48.29	2.167
7-Iodo-2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromone.	225	Yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₃ IS	42.79	2.000	42.07	1.892
6-Chloro-2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromone.	204	Greenish yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₃ ClS	56.50	2.700	56.02	2.514
6-Bromo-2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromone.	218	Brownish yellow needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₃ BrS	38.31	2.480	48.29	2.480
6-Iodo-2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromone.	218	Brownish needles.	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₃ IS	42.81	2.130	42.07	1.892

Preparation of 6- and 7-halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)-4-chromanones (VI a—b), Table No. 6 : 4'-Bromo-2'-hydroxy-3-(2'-thienyl)-acrylophenone (1.5 g) was dissolved in aqueous alcohol (75%, 35 ml) and sodium acetate (1 g) was added to adjust the pH of the solution between 4 and 5. The solution was refluxed for 24 hrs. It was then cooled and poured over ice. The dry solid obtained was crystallised from petroleum ether (60°–80°) in colourless needles (VI b). Yield 25%.

TABLE 6

6- and 7-Halogeno-2-(2-thienyl)-chromanones (VI b&a)

Compounds	M.P. °C	Colour and crystalline shape	Molecular formula	Found		Required	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
7-Chloro-2-(2-thienyl)- chromanone.	93	Colourless needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ ClS	60.50	3.586	58.98	3.402
7-Bromo-2-(2-thienyl)- chromanone.	110	Colourless needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ BrS	50.00	3.201	50.49	2.912
7-Iodo-2-(2-thienyl)- chromanone.	140	Colourless needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ IS	43.20	2.583	43.82	2.527
6-Bromo-2-(2-thienyl)- chromanone.	101	Colourless needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ BrS	49.90	3.222	50.48	2.920
6-Iodo-2-(2-thienyl)- chromanone.	125	Colourless needles.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ IS	43.52	2.927	43.82	2.527

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